

The Types of Questions Used by the Teacher in Reading Class at MTs As'adiyah Ereng-Ereng Bantaeng

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Abstract:

This research highlights the types of questions used by the teacher in Reading Class which focused on teacher's question, types of the question and the length of students' responses. The research was conducted at MTs As'adiyah Ereng-Ereng Bantaeng, the researcher chose one English teacher purposively. This research applied qualitative descriptive and discourse analysis as a research design to analyze language, writing, speech, and conversation (verbal and non-verbal). The data was collected through classroom observation and interview. One teacher was involved as a subject of this research. The data were analyzed based on three procedures of data analysis which were involved in data collection, data analysis and interpretation. The result of this research shows that (1) the teacher performed both types of question from Lidya's Genre of question they are less sophisticated and sophisticated questions. In this research less sophisticated question emerged 328 times in three meetings observation. This level of question become most used level of question because basically the teacher asked question to recall the material that they have been learned before in order to involve the students' participation and to recall their memory in their teacher and learning process especially memory that related to the words meaning. In contrast, sophisticated question only appeared 106 times. The sophisticated questions demand the students to use their imagination, developed unique ideas, think creatively and making some judgment related to the teaching material based on the specific criterion. (2) The reason why teacher ask questions dominated by checking the students' understanding about the material. The types of questions asked were determined by pedagogical purposes the teacher wanted to achieve. (3) The question that achieves the longest response was less sophisticated questions (more-than-ten-words) based on the length of students' responses and followed by sophisticated question (seven-to-ten-words) it means that when this type of question asked, the students' response was shorter.

INTRODUCTION

English as the one of the subjects taught in school reading comprehension in particular is expected to increase the knowledge, skills, attitudes, and value contained therein. Reading at any level is taught to enable the learners to develop basic comprehension skills, so that they

can read and understand texts of a general nature (Adams, 1994). Harmer (2001) defines the reading comprehension skills as abilities to extract the required information from written text as efficiently as possible. As it is written in Oxford Dictionary (1991: 286), comprehension is the capacity for understanding fully; the act or action of grasping with the intellect. Reading is to understand the meaning of written or printed materials.

In the last several decades, theories and models of reading have changed, from seeing reading as primarily receptive processes from text to reader to interactive processes between the reader and the text (Adams, 1994; Carrell, et al., 1988; Pham & Hasson 2014; Unrau & Ruddell, 2004). Approaches to the teaching of foreign language reading have attempted to reflect this development through interactive exercises and tasks. The use of questions is an integral aspect of such activities in the classroom, and in their experiences as language teachers have seen that well-designed comprehension questions help students interact with the text to create or construct meaning.

Two language competencies tested on English National Exam from 2015 until 2019 are listening and reading, yet reading has the most numbers in the exams (Uswatunnisa, 2020). In reality, reading is difficult skill in language especially the students who are still difficult to understand the content of the reading text. Generally, the teachers only provide text for the students and teachers ask students to read and look for the answer of the existing text with aids namely English dictionary and the students do it individually or work with their partner.

However, in the classroom, teacher's questioning plays a very important role to initiate classroom talk. It is evident that a question can stimulate students' motivation, focus their attention, and help students to learn and think better, and also help the teacher to know how well a student's learning is (Lim, 2011; Dillon, 2004). There have been many research studies which revealed teachers preferred to ask plenty of questions with different purposes in the classroom (Larsen-Freeman 2016; Tarone 2007; Seliger & Long, 1983; Allwright, 1997). Obviously, during the process of teaching and learning, teacher's questioning plays a crucial role in the classroom. Question-and-answer activity is viewed as the most common form of communication between students and teachers in the classroom.

Roshenshine as cited in Brown (2001) suggest that during the teaching and learning process, teacher questions have an influence to the students' achievement in learning and thinking. A good question will guide the students in forming answer or response more meaningfully. Beside that the questions should really be meaningful to the students. Therefore, teacher should know the types of questions and how they can be used for different purposes. The skill of using questions effectively in the learning process is the responsibility of the teacher as a leader during learning and teaching activities. The skill depends on the techniques of the teaching asking questions (Widodo & Pujiastuti, 2006). When the teacher questions are well planned then the question can lead the students on learning experience that they desired as Brown and Abeywickrama (2010) states that questioning practice is good to increase students' conceptual knowledge, develop knowledge of text's structure, and enhance the use of text processing strategies.

Speaking of questions used by the teacher, there two kinds of taxonomy which generally used to identify kinds of questions posed by teacher when they are teaching. Those are Barret and Bloom's Taxonomy. Barrett taxonomy categorizes reading comprehension skills into five levels of comprehension. They are presented in the hierarchy from the lowest to the highest level of reading; they are literal, reorganization, inference, evaluation and appreciation (Fitria, et al., 2017). On the other hand, Bloom Taxonomy is one of taxonomy that has long been used in Indonesia (Widodo, 2005). Bloom divides six types of questions to develop students' thinking skills. The taxonomy consists of knowledge, comprehension, application, analysis, synthesis, and evaluation questions. Knowledge questions demand to recognize and recall information that has been learned by the students. Comprehension questions demand the students to be able to demonstrate their understanding about the material. Application questions require the students to apply the information they have learned. Analysis involves three kinds of psychological process which are identifying, considering and analyzing the information to reach a conclusion and the last evaluation questions, it requires the students to assess the benefits of an idea, solve the problem, and explore their opinion.

Barret and Bloom taxonomy is widely accepted as guidelines for teachers in building up the students' cognitive skills. It can be applied to assess learning on a variety of cognitive levels from lower-to higher-order thinking. It is commonly used s assessment techniques, assigning grade and initiating student's response feedback. It has been used as the guide lines by the teacher in Indonesian education system from the elementary level until tertiary level (Widodo & Pujiastuti, 2006; Gunawan & Palupi, 2016; Novarina, 2013).

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Referring to an amount of information mentioned above, the researcher therefore is responsible to figure out sufficient information to explain the types of questions used by the teacher in reading class, the reason of using questions and the effect of questions on the response of the students in reading class (during the process of teaching reading)

Talking Teacher's questions-students' response is usually characterized by communicative pattern where the main goal of learning is communicative skill oriented by integrating all four-language skill (reading, listening, writing and speaking) (Sadiku, 2015; Yanfen & Yuqin, 2010). Since reading is a very important skill for the students, great attention also should be paid to the teaching of reading, particularly to the teacher's role in reading activities. It is due to the fact that a teacher has an important role in teaching reading as what Kharizmi (2019) states that a teacher plays important role in the classroom teaching. A teacher is the most important person reading class deciding the kind of experience the children should have. More explicitly, Boliti (2013) confirm that teacher is variable underlying students' success in learning to read. It is an obligation for the teacher to stimulate

student's interest in reading; they must help the students to see that reading is valuable skill for them. The students are able of course, to do the learning themselves, but the teacher has a major effect in reading activity and create materials appropriate in sequence of increasing difficulty which leads to the students' improvement in reading skill as what Artu (2016) states that to bring students and give appropriate materials altogether are very large parts of the reading teacher's job. Meanwhile, the teacher also must provide practice and introduce reading strategies.

Regarding the reading strategies, questioning is one of the types commonly used by the English teacher in their reading EFL classes. In line with this, Carlsen (1991) found out that the teacher's question vary from 30 to 120 questions per hour. While (Brock, 1986) states that 80% of classroom activities are devoted asking, answering, and reacting to questioning. Therefore, by conducting some questioning activities, it is expected to stimulate students' asking questioning skill, to promote their thought and understand the ideas, to be able to diagnose and recall information, and to activate students' knowledge background (Chin 2007). Moreover, based on the previous findings conducted by Long and Sato (1983) that questions and answer are very common activities if they are exploited appropriately, they can help the students and the teachers to judge usefulness of what they are doing. In line with this, David (2007) furthermore states that questions play central role in reading comprehension instruction because they can develop concept, build background, clarify reasoning process, and even to lead students to the higher level of thinking. Therefore, posing questioning can be a useful tool for a skillful teacher to serve numerous useful learning purposes and encourage students' level of thinking.

METHOD

This study employs qualitative research method as the research design, this method was chosen because it matched with the characteristics of the research questions. Mills and Gay (2019) the qualitative method deal with the collection, analysis, and interpretation of comprehensive and narrative data in order to gain insight into particular phenomenon of interest. Therefore, the purpose of qualitative research focused and deals with promoting a deep understanding of particular phenomenon such as environment, a process, or even belief.

Furthermore, in this research, the researcher applied discourse analysis as an approach to analyze the language, writing, speech, and conversation (verbal and non- verbal). Indeed, the researcher employed discourse analysis as an approach that is suitable with the purpose of this research in order to get the description about the types of questions, the reason why ask questions, and the effect of the questions on the length of the students' response in classroom interaction. In order to get the data, the researcher conducted the observation, recording and interview.

Mills and Gay (2019) said that in observation the researcher obtains the data by watching the participants. Furthermore, by explain that there are two commonly types of observation namely participant observation and non-participant observation. This case the researcher applied non-participant observation in which the researcher did not participate in the activity that has been observed as Setyosari (2016) state that using non-participant

observation is easier to record information and observation if the researcher does not participate so that the researcher can record the data more easily. The researcher only observed the teacher questions during the teaching and learning process in the classroom. The observation was recorded. The observation has taken for three meetings and also a recorder was settled to record classroom interaction and the observation intended to answer the first and the third research questions of this research. In analyzing the data, the researcher firstly transcribed all observation and interview. The process of transcribing allowed the researcher to become acquainted with the data (Bertaux & Thompson, 2006). The researcher processed the data using Microsoft word.

There were some theories in analyzing the data, according to Mills and Gay (2019) states that the process of analyzing the qualitative research data consist of three steps, namely reading, describing and classifying. Meanwhile, Borg (2006) has step by step guidelines; those are familiarizing the researcher with the data, generating initial code, the researcher read through each transcript to immerse in the data, reviewing themes, defining and naming themes, and producing the report. Therefore, the researcher adopted these steps in analyzing the data based on the objective of the research.

In applied the step guidelines above, the researcher firstly familiarized herself with the data through listen to the data. Then, for generating initial code, the researcher transcribed the data get from observation and interview. After that the researcher would have the data transcribed in order to be immersed to the data. Furthermore, the researcher reviewed the themes by separating the discourse needed from transcribed. After the researcher define and name themes or discourse needed into types of questions, then finally the researcher produced the report of the discourse analysis data.

In addition, in order to find out the effect of questions asked by the teacher or students' production of the target language and types of responses have been given, the transcript was analyzed by calculating the average length (number of words) of students' responses to the types of teachers' questions, similar to Brock (1986), only those responses that immediately followed the teachers' eliciting moves were considered, once the teacher spoke again, the responses were considered have ended. After doing classroom observation and analyzing the data, the researches executed interview session, the researcher applied the semi-structured interview; the researcher had the general ideas of how he or she wants to interview unfold and may even have a set of prepared questions. The interview was conducted to obtain the reason why the teacher asks certain types of questions. The semi-structured interview is used in this study because its questions have no choice from which the interviewee selects the answer (McMillan & Schumacher, 1990). Thus, interviewee felt free to answer the interview questions.

This research took place at MTs As'adiyah Ereng-Ereng Bantaeng, Makassar South Sulawesi. The participant of this research was an English Teacher who graduated from UIN Alauddin Makassar in 2010. This teacher has been teaching English for almost eight years in this school. Besides teaching at junior high school level, she also teaches at senior high school at MA As'adiyah Ereng-Ereng for English subject.

FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

Based on the work of Benjamin Bloom and Barret T.C. the researcher developed the genre for classifying the types of question.

Table 1. Categories of Questions

Bloom Taxonomy	Barret Taxonomy	Lidya's Genre of Questions
Knowledge/Comprehension	Literal Comprehension	Less Sophisticated Question
Application/Analysis	Reorganization	
Synthesis	Inferential Comprehension	Sophisticated Question
Evaluation	Evaluation/Appreciation	

Table 1 shows the relationship between Lidya's genre of question, Bloom Taxonomy, and Barret Taxonomy. The Lidya's genre of question is basically a two-genre of question that combines knowledge, comprehension, application, analysis, synthesis and evaluation categories of Bloom Taxonomy. In addition, it also combines five of Barret categories from lower level of thinking into higher level. The categories of questions that make up Lidya's genre of question are less sophisticated and sophisticated.

Types of question used by the teacher

The result findings exemplifies that there are two types of questions used by the teacher in teaching reading

Less sophisticated questions

Less sophisticated question is the lowest level of questions that the teacher poses in teaching and learning process. It has the simple pattern questions among all the levels. It is posed to find the answer of the problem expected in answer is drawn directly from the content of instruction. Therefore, this level of question existed most times in the conversation between teacher and students in the classroom interaction. Less sophisticated questions are mostly happening in the classroom when the teacher give questions and directly answer by the students. It requires a low-level thinking question which invokes lower cognitive processing such as memorizing facts, concrete information, etc. that requires the students 'memory. At this level the students also demanding to integrate or analyze remembered or given information and supply a single, correct predictable answer, although they may involve more thinking the students only expected to arrive at a correct and predictable answer. These levels of questions were evidently found 328 times from three meetings observation.

Sophisticated Questions

Sophisticated question is the highest level of the teacher question in teaching and learning process. It can be defined as the question that requires the students to use their imagination, develops unique idea and think creatively, and put value on something or make some kinds of judgment. This open-ended question requires the students to use related information while applying internal or external criteria to make judgment. The responses of this question often be limited predictor by a number of choices. It has the simple pattern of questions among all the levels. Sophisticated questions were posed to find out the answer to

problem expected in directly answering from the content of instruction. Based on the data observation that has been conducted by the researcher from three meetings observation, it was found that the total of the sophisticated questions surfaced were about 74 times in the first meeting, 21 times in the second meeting and none in the last or third meeting.

The reason why teacher asked questions

During classroom interaction among the teacher and students, the questions that are asked by the teacher have many reasons behind them. Based on the extract in the findings section, it can be found that there are several reasons why the teacher asked questions. Those reasons are presented below:

Assessing students' prior knowledge

Teacher sometimes wanted to know the students' prior knowledge before explained about the material. The reason why the teacher need to assess the students' prior knowledge is new knowledge to build upon what one already knows and believes so prior knowledge can hinder or block the students from learning new material and the other reason is to know how far the students' knowledge. "If a student' initial ideas and beliefs are ignored, the understanding that they develop can be very different from what the teacher intends" (Branford, et al. in Garfield and Ben-Zvi, 2008), so that's why the teacher needs to know the students prior knowledge. This reason also similar to what Mayberry & Hartle (in Prasetyawati, 2015) said that the teacher asked questions to assess the students prior knowledge.

Checking students' understanding

The teacher always used questions in the process of teaching and learning if he or she wanted to check the students' understanding. This similar with this research which the teacher said that most of time she used questions was to check students understanding. This condition is similar with Prasetyawati (2015) and Nugroho (2011), to know whether the students understand what teacher explained, the teacher frequently used questions to check students' understanding.

Getting students to think

During the process of teaching and learning, getting a student to think is a must. In this research, the teacher asked the students to make their own sentences or expression in the target language in order to get them to think about the translation and critical thinking. This related to Peacock (as cited in Borg, 2006), the reason why teacher ask questions is for students to stimulate and develop their thinking during the process of teaching and learning.

Encouraging students' participation

One way to make the class more interactive is asking the students to be more active in the classroom. In this research, the teacher ask the students to mention the day in that time and to pronounce the year before starting their lesson by using the target language to encourage the students to participate in a lesson. This similar with Jack et al. (1994) and Borg (2006) mention that to stimulate the students' participation in the classroom, by asking the questions is needed.

Stimulating students' interest

Stimulating the students' interest in the process of learning language is one reason why the teacher used questions. In this research the teacher stated that she asked questions. Because she wanted to stimulate the students' interest. This is similar with Prasetyawati (2015), she also found in her research that one of the reasons why the teacher asked question in elementary school was to stimulate the students' interest.

Encouraging the students to focus

Asking the students to focus on a lesson is sometimes needed by the teacher. In this research, the teacher said that she used questions to encourage the students to focus on the content of the lesson. Sometimes the teacher needs to explain more and more about the material to the students. As Rohmah (2003) and Shomoossi (2004) said that questions can be used to help students to focus back to the lesson.

Making the students to do more practice with their pronunciation

One of the important elements in learning language is a pronunciation, so that's why the students need to always practice the target language by pronunciation. In this research, the teacher said that she asked the students to pronounce some English because it would be benefit for them before the teacher explained about the material in that day which was letter. This is similar with Miller (2011) said that pronunciation is just not just producing the right sound or stressing the right syllables, it is also helping the students understand what they hear.

The effect of questions based on students' responses

From the result of the current research, it can be found that when less sophisticated questions were asked by the English teacher in MTs As'adiyah Ereng-Ereng Bantaeng, the students' responses are longest. This can be discovered in one student's responses, for example, "*That is very kind of you, but I can manage myself*", and "*The text is about to spend my school holiday in Texas, December in New York and....*" It can be concluded that the responses for less sophisticated questions are the most among other questions.

For sophisticated questions, the students' responses are varied (one-word, until seven-to-ten-words) but mostly in one word answer. This can be found in some of the students' responses, for example, "*benar*", "*tidak*", "*tolong menolong*", and "*Could you help me untied this rope?*".

CONCLUSION

Based on the results and the discussion, the following conclusions can be drawn:

Firstly, in this research less sophisticated question from Lidya's Genre of question emerged 328 times in three meetings observation. This level of question become most used level of question because basically the teacher asked question to recall the material that they have been learned before in order to involve the students' participation and to recall their memory in their teacher and learning process especially memory that related to the words meaning. In contrast, sophisticated question only appeared 106 times. This level of question categorized as the highest level of question which only implemented in the first and the second meeting. The sophisticated questions demands the students to use their imagination,

developed unique ideas, think creatively and making some judgment related to the teaching material based on the specific criterion.

Secondly, from the whole process of teaching and learning in the three meetings, the reason why teacher asks questions was to assess students' prior knowledge, checking the students' understanding, getting the students to think, encouraging the students' participation, enable the teacher to clarify what the students have said, encouraging the students to focus and making the students do more practice in their pronunciation.

Thirdly, the question that received the longest response is the less sophisticated questions (more-than-ten-words) based on the length of students' responses and the sophisticated question only seven-to-ten-words response.

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